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Review Article

A Review on Herbs Used in Face Serum

Vishakha Borkar*, Vidya Waghamare, Shubham Kakde

Dnyansadhana College Of Pharmacy, Parbhani.

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ABSTRACT

World has now come to the realization that herbal formulations are safer and more effective than synthetic ones. It increases the global demand for herbal formulations. The primary purpose of herbal cosmetics is to preserve and protect an individual's look. Face serum has the ability to swiftly penetrate the skin's layers. Customers searching for skincare products that are both Ecofriendly and effective are increasingly choosing herbal face serums. Serum offers a rich, non-greasy composition with a high concentration of active ingredients, as well as quick absorption and the capacity to penetrate the skin's deeper layers. The serum has the ability to penetrate deeper layers of the skin and has the quality of rapid absorption. Because of their powerful botanical ingredients and skin-nourishing properties, herbal face serums are becoming more and more well-liked as natural skincare treatments. Plant extracts, essential oils, and bioactive substances are used in the formulation of these serums to hydrate, revitalize, and shield the skin. Herbal alternatives to traditional serums employ fewer synthetic chemicals, which lowers the possibility of discomfort and negative responses. Many people use herbal cosmetics on a regular basis, and they are quite necessary in today's environment. The current review represents the different types of face serum with herbs used in face serum, Advantages, Disadvantages and Marketed Formulation.

INTRODUCTION

Study of human skin is crucial in fields like dermatology, toxicology, pharmacology, and cosmetology, as it helps understand how external agents affect the skin, how they interact, and their potential toxicity. The desire for beauty and healthy skin has been important since ancient

times, and this led to the development of cosmetics. The word "cosmetic" comes from the Greek word meaning "to adorn," and cosmetology is the science of beautifying and improving skin, nails, and In skincare, the goal is to deliver active ingredients effectively into the skin without harmful chemicals. Face serums are a solution for this, as they concentrate powerful ingredients to give quicker, more noticeable results. A serum is

***Corresponding Author:** Vishakha Borkar

Address: Dnyansadhana College of Pharmacy, Parbhani.

Email ✉: vish.borkar92@gmail.com

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much more concentrated than a cream, containing up to ten times more active ingredients, either in water or oil form, making it a key product in cosmetology. Serum is packed with a bunch of beneficiary active components and nutrients such as antioxidants, Ceramides, amino acids and others. This explains why face serum always being the costliest item in a skin care Set. Weather it is moisturizer, anti-wrinkle or anti-aging product or skin serum, all these products should contain Antioxidants, cell-communicating ingredients and skin identical ingredients.

Serum

Its gets rapidly absorbed and easily penetrates into the deeper layers of the skin. Also has a non-greasy finish and intensive formula which contains high concentrations of active substances. It contains skin- smoothing ingredients that enhance skin texture and make skin soft, silky smooth, and fair. The formulation has good spreadability makes the pores appear smaller increase moisture level.

Types Of Serum

1.The Oil Serum

The oil serum is the simplest to make of all the face serums. It often starts with a base of just premium, fast-Absorbing carrier oils, also referred to as “dry” oils. In addition to having moisturising and barrier- repairing Characteristics, the premium oils used in the serum also include polyphenols, essential fatty acids, and other Substances that may be broken down by the skin.

2.The Gel Serum

The gel serum Gel serums provide the skin a “tightening” sensation, giving your consumer the impression that their skin is Momentarily lifted or tightened in particular regions of the face. The gel serum provides you the chance to Include some

fantastic water-based (hydrophilic) plant extracts because this formulation is water-based, plant extract because this formulation is water based

3. The Water Based Serum

Water-based serums are comparable to gel serums, although they may contain none or very little gums and thickeners to administer high-performance hydrophilic plant extracts that are trapped against the skin beneath A cream or lotion would utilise a water based face serum. Layering an anti-ageing face mist under an Emulsion

4 .The Emulsion Serum

An emulsion-based face serum is a moisturizer that strength the skin barrier function while also delivering high performance component to the skin Emulsifier is used to bind water and oil together and retain them in stable state. The Best chance of delivering high performance active dipely into the tissue of the skin through an emulsion Given the skin barrier function it is highly difficult for any cosmetic component to penetrate dermis yet an oil and water mixture is best suited to accomplish this remarkable feat The skin barrier function will be straight by the emulsion moisturising character

5. The Pressed Balm Serum

A balm serum has a conventional balm basis of butters, waxes, and oils but also includes active substances that Are oil soluble (lipophilic) and may help the skin. The butters and waxes form an occlusive barrier on the skin That hydrates and nourishes it while allowing the pressed serum’s active components to do their job. In a balm Serum, dozens of intriguing unique butters and waxes can be combined with thousands of exquisite plant oils.

Advantages of face serum:

1. Improves skin texture.
2. Minimizes the skin pores.
3. Reduces fine lines and wrinkles.
4. Evens the skin tone.
5. Hydrates and nourishes the skin.
6. Improves skin elasticity.
7. Reduces dark circles.

8. Protects from the free radicals.

Disadvantages of face serum:

1. Face serums might come with a higher price tag compared to other skincare products.
2. Individuals with sensitive skin might experience irritation, redness, or breakout

Herbs Used In Formulation Of Herbal Face Serum

SR NO	Name of Plants	Chemical Constituents	Function Properties	Plants Parts used in Face Serum	Image of Plants
1	Aloe vera	Amino acids, polysaccharides, minerals, organic acids, phenolic compounds, anthrones, C-glycosides	Anti-inflammatory, anti-itch, pain reduction, wound healing, antioxidant properties	Aloe vera Gel	
2	Liquorice	Glycyrrhizin, flavonoids, coumarins, triterpenoids	Anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, antimicrobial, hepatoprotective	Roots	

3	Lavender	Linalool, linalyl acetate, lavandulyl acetate	Relaxant, anti-anxiety, anti-inflammatory	Essential oil of Flowers	
4	Rosemary	Rosmarinic acid, carnosic acid, ursolic acid	Antioxidant, anti-inflammatory	Leaves	
5	Ginseng	Ginsenosides	Adaptogenic, immune-boosting properties	Roots and leaves	
6		Apigenin	Relaxant, anti-inflammatory	Flower oil	
7	Almond	Oleic acid, linoleic acid, vitamin E	Moisturizing, anti-aging, skin barrier repair	Almond Oil	

8	Coconut	Lauric acid, caprylic acid, vitamin E	Moisturizing, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory	Coconut Oil	
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Marketed Formulation

How To Use Face Serum

Cleanse your skin: Start by washing your face. Use a gentle cleanser that is appropriate for your skin type to remove any debris, oil, and pollutants from your skin. Use a fresh towel to pat dry your skin.

Tone (optional): If you use a toner as part of your skincare routine, apply it only after cleaning. Toners can aid in restoring equilibrium to the skin's pH levels and prepare it for improved absorption of the upcoming skin care regimen.

Apply serum: Apply a pea-sized amount of face serum with your fingertips. As you may remember, a little goes a long way, so don't need to use a lot of serum.

Apply to face:

Gently pat the serum onto your skin, beginning in the center and going outward. Refrain from twisting or tugging at the skin near the delicate eye area. Use light, upward strokes to massage the serum into your skin. Focus on trouble spots or regions.

like wrinkles, dark spots, or fine lines where you want to treat specific skincare

CONCLUSION

These days, there are a fantastic number of serums on the market for every skin type and skin issue, so it's critical to know exactly what you want in a serum. Herbal face serums are a natural and effective option for anyone looking for light yet effective skincare solutions. Herbal face serums reduce the risk of adverse reactions that are commonly associated with synthetic components while meeting a wide range of skincare needs, from moisturizing and nourishing to calming and energizing. From the above review it was concluded that the herbs like alovera, almond oil, coconut oil ginseng, rosemary, lavender, liquorice are effective in maintaining skin nourish and free from any skin problems when used in face serum. Given customers growing demand for clean and green beauty products, herbal face serums are an eco-friendly and versatile solution that provides a full skincare program that improve both appearance and wellbeing.

REFERENCES

1. Shimpi AA, Pawara AS. A Review on Herbal Face Pack. *Research Journal of Pharmacology and Pharmacodynamics*. 2022
2. Thorat PS, Bhadane HB, Wagh SS, Gaikwad MS, Chhajed SS. General review on face serum. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*; c2023.

3. Kaur L, Singh AP, Singh AP, Kaur T. A review on herbal cosmetics. *Intional Jornel Pharm Drug Anal* 2021.
4. Mileva M, Ilieva Y, Jovtchev G, Gateva S, Zaharieva MM, Georgieva A, et al. Rose flowers – A delicate perfume or a natural healer? *Biomolecules*. 2021.
5. Mishra, A. K., Mishra, A., & Chattopadhyay, P., Herbal cosmeceuticals for photoprotection from ultraviolet B radiation: A review, *Tropical Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 2011;.
6. Khan, N., Ahmed, S., Sheraz, M. A., Anwar, Z., & Ahmad, I. (). *Pharmaceutical based cosmetic serums*. In *Profiles of Drug Substances, Excipients and Related Methodology*, Academic Press, 2023 .
7. Miss. Purva S Rajdev, Prof. Gaikwad S.D, Miss Akanksha A Somvanshi, Miss. Shubhangi Gunjal. *Formulation and evaluation of face serum*.
8. Khan Thalha N, Pawar Shankar B, Dapkekar sambhaji A, Shinde Pallavi M, Datkhile Sachin V. *Formulation and wvaluation of herbal face serum*.

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